

DEVELOPMENT OF RENEWABLE ENERGY SOURCES ON THE SCALE OF UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: The article deals with important information about development of renewable energy sources on the scale of Uzbekistan. Moreover, it covers the latest date about the topic.

Key words: *large-scale transition, energy-related, public-private, financial organisations, co-operating, co-generationa plants, energy consumption.*

Uzbekistan's energy sector is currently undergoing a large-scale transition. The key institutions and stakeholders for energy policy making and its implementation are summarised below. The **Ministry of Energy**, established in February 2019, has overall responsibility for the development and implementation of energy policies, plans and programmes, and is authorised to play a central role in implementing renewable energy policy in Uzbekistan. It is also responsible for the regulation and supervision of the production, transmission, distribution and consumption of energy resources including electricity and the functioning of energy sectors, as well as the implementation of production-sharing agreements. Moreover, the ministry takes part in developing energy-related public-private partnerships (PPPs) and plays a role in improving the tariff policy in co-operation with the inter-ministerial tariff council to facilitate the development of a competitive business environment.

The **Ministry of Finance** exercises price regulation, including tariff-setting for electricity, and general control over the financial stability of the state sector, among other functions. Moreover, the PPP Development Agency under the Ministry of Finance plays a key role in developing PPPs in co-operation with

Ministry of Investment and Foreign Trade and the Ministry of Energy. The **Ministry of Investment and Foreign Trade** is responsible for implementing the state investment policy, including foreign direct investments in the energy sector, and co-operating with international financial institutions and foreign governmental financial organisations[1]. It is also responsible for devising and co-ordinating state policies on foreign trade and international economic co-operation. The **Ministry of Economic Development and Poverty Reduction** is in charge of analysing and forecasting macroeconomic indicators and development based on proposed economic management market mechanisms and strategies to develop the main industries, including energy. The ministry also formulates strategies for industrial development in Uzbekistan based on the effective deployment of production forces, rations and food production.

The **Cabinet of Ministers** approves the rules for electricity and gas use and monitors investment programmes in the energy industry. The **State Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Statistics** is the official authority collecting energy statistics. It will play an important role in the future in collecting data on off-grid solar photovoltaics and solar heat use in households. The **Thermal Power Plants joint-stock company (JSC)**, a thermal power generation company, operates the majority of thermal power facilities in Uzbekistan, consisting of ten thermal power companies. As of 2021, Thermal Power Plants operates 11 thermal power plants, including co-generation plants, with an installed capacity of 11 669 MW. Formerly, the power sector in Uzbekistan was vertically integrated and Uzbekenergo, a state-owned monopoly, was in charge of power generation, transmission, distribution and retail service, while serving the function of planning, investment, daily operation and regulation of the sector[2]. With a view to strengthening competition in the sector, a decision was made in March 2019 to unbundle Uzbekenergo into three JSCs: Thermal Power Plants JSC, the National Electric Grid of Uzbekistan JSC and the Regional Electric Power Networks JSC.

Uzbekhydroenergo JSC is a state-owned company which operates hydropower plants, another important source of energy in Uzbekistan. The company was separated from **Uzbekenergo JSC** and established in May 2017. In total, it operates 37 hydropower plants with an installed capacity of 1 853 MW (EBRD, 2020). The **National Electric Grid of Uzbekistan JSC**, the systems operator, is responsible for implementing centralised operational dispatch of all power plants and for operating transmission networks. The **Regional Electric Power Networks JSC** is in charge of local electricity distribution. Its distribution and sales to consumers are handled by 14 territorial JSCs under its management.

The constant increase in energy consumption, the increase in the cost of electricity, the limited reserves of fossil fuels and the negative impact on the environment of power plants operating on fossil fuels - all this leads to the question of the need to switch to renewable energy sources. The solution of this issue is especially relevant for Uzbekistan, the energy system of which has a high degree of centralization. Almost 85% of the total volume of electricity is generated by large power plants, after which the electricity is fed into the general extensive power grid[3]. This level of centralization of the energy system is typical for densely populated districts and some regions of Tashkent, while sparsely populated areas of Tashkent and a number of regions of the Far East (together forming a significant part of the territory of Uzbekistan) are characterized by a low level of connection to centralized energy systems. At the same time, it is not possible to lay high-voltage transmission lines to supply power to remote and sparsely populated villages, cities and industries from an economic and technical point of view.

One of the possible solutions to this problem is the use of diesel or gasoline generators, which have a number of advantages and allow you to achieve the goals set for uninterrupted power supply to remote consumers. However, when considering the issue of providing electricity to consumers who have the first (or

first special) category for the reliability of power supply, one cannot be limited to only one energy source. Failure of a diesel generator can result in significant financial damage, danger to human life and a threat to the country's security. Touching upon the environmental side of the issue of power supply to remote consumers, we note that the use of diesel generators creates conditions for environmental degradation (exhaust gases, loud noise, the risk of fuel and oil spills), therefore, when solving this problem, it is necessary to reduce the use of diesel generators to a minimum. In general, the region of decentralized energy supply of the Far East includes 987 thousand people and 360 settlements. The total installed capacity of diesel power plants is 670 MW. The real crisis in the power supply of the Far Eastern Federal District has led to the question of the need to use renewable energy sources. But in order to have a sufficient idea of the efficiency of RES in this region, let us consider the summary data on the potential of the Far East region in the field of renewable energy.

Modeling is one of the most important stages in the design of a mobile power complex for decentralized power supply, in the process of which it is necessary to consider many factors and parameters before deciding on the device of an independent power supply system, including the components of generation and storage of energy. The most important moments for design are the type of renewable energy sources used, the amount of energy they can generate, climatic, topographic and geographical parameters of the area, the type of loads and the specificity of the need for electricity. The power complex consists of the following components: a solar photovoltaic plant (SFEU), a wind power plant (WPP), a diesel power plant (DPP) and energy storage units (batteries), which are connected to a DC bus to coordinate the operating modes of the power complex components with each other and are connected to the useful and ballast load[4]. The complex should provide the consumer with a continuous supply of electricity, while he should use the potential of renewable energy sources to the maximum,

and if they are not enough, start supplying the consumer with energy from a diesel generator. In the event of a short-term power shortage, it is necessary to use an installed energy storage device (battery pack), switchable (one is switched on for charging, and the other for discharge). A situation is possible when the consumer's load is small, and the energy storage device is fully charged, the diesel generator is off, and renewable sources generate more energy than necessary, then it is necessary to apply a ballast load to consume excess electricity. In any other situation, the ballast load must be disconnected.

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